

Arginase Dysregulation in Neurodegenerative Diseases: Metabolic and Cellular Dysfunction and Therapeutic Implications

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Abstract

Neurodegenerative diseases are increasingly recognized as disorders associated with metabolic dysfunction with arginine metabolism emerging as a significant contributor. Arginase, by regulating the balance between arginine and ornithine, is positioned at the crossroads of multiple arginine metabolic pathways, thereby controlling a variety of cellular processes essential for proper brain homeostasis. Chronic disruption of these pathways may lead to dysfunction of neurons and glia ultimately resulting in the induction of neurodegenerative processes.

In this review, based on data from patients and experimental models, we synthesize and critically evaluate evidence demonstrating alterations in arginase isoenzymes and associated metabolic pathways in Alzheimer's Parkinson's and Huntington's diseases, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. We discuss mechanisms through which dysregulation of arginase and arginine metabolism may contribute to neurodegeneration, including disturbances in nitrogen metabolism, oxidative and nitrosative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and neuroinflammation.

Based on this body of evidence, we propose therapeutic strategies targeting arginase-related pathways, with the aim of preserving cellular metabolic homeostasis to ameliorate disease progression. Finally, we outline directions for future research, emphasizing that a proper understanding of the physiological roles of arginase isoenzymes and their disease-, stage-, and cell-specific dysregulation will be essential for the development of effective metabolically targeted therapies against neurodegenerative diseases.

Keywords

arginase, arginine, nitric oxide, polyamines, ammonia, urea, neurodegeneration, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Huntington's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis

Abbreviations

3-NPA, 3-nitropropionic acid; 3-NT, 3-nitrotyrosine; 3xTg, triple-transgenic Alzheimer's disease mouse model; 6-OHDA, 6-hydroxydopamine; α Syn, alpha-synuclein; A β , amyloid- β ; AD, Alzheimer's disease; ADC, arginine decarboxylase; AGAT, arginine:glycine amidinotransferase; Agm, agmatine ALS, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; APP, amyloid precursor protein; APP/PS1, amyloid precursor protein/presenilin-1 transgenic Alzheimer's disease mouse model; Arg, arginine; Arg1, arginase 1; Arg2, arginase 2; ASL, argininosuccinate lyase; ASS, argininosuccinate synthase; BBB, blood-brain barrier; BDNF, brain-derived neurotrophic factor; CBF, cerebral blood flow; Cit, citrulline; CNS, central nervous system; CPS, carbamoyl phosphate synthetase; Cre, creatine; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; CVN-AD, APP quadruple mutant Alzheimer's disease mouse model on inducible NOS-null background; DFMO, difluoromethylornithine; ECx, entorhinal cortex; eNOS, endothelial nitric oxide synthase; FTD, frontotemporal dementia; GAA, guanidinoacetic acid; GABA, γ -aminobutyric acid; Glu, glutamate; GS, glutamine synthetase; HD, Huntington's disease; Hdh^{(CAG)¹⁵⁰}, knock-in Huntington's disease mouse model with 150 CAG repeat huntingtin; HTT, huntingtin; iNOS, inducible nitric oxide synthase; KO, knockout; M1, classically activated (pro-inflammatory) macrophages/microglia; M2, alternatively activated (anti-inflammatory) macrophages/microglia; MAO-B, monoamine oxidase B; MCI, mild cognitive impairment; MCU, mitochondrial calcium uniporter; MPTP, 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine; MSA, multiple system atrophy; MSNs, medium spiny neurons; NMDAR, N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor; nNOS, neuronal nitric oxide synthase; NO, nitric oxide; NOS, nitric oxide synthase; NOx, nitrates + nitrites; OAT, ornithine aminotransferase; ODC, ornithine decarboxylase; Orn, ornithine; OTC, ornithine transcarbamylase; OXPHOS, oxidative phosphorylation; P5C, pyrroline-5-carboxylate; PD, Parkinson's disease; PET, positron emission tomography; polyQ, polyglutamine expansion; Pro, proline; PS1, presenilin-1; PS19, P301S tau transgenic mouse model; PSP, progressive supranuclear palsy; Put, putrescine; Q57, huntingtin with 57 glutamines; R6/2, exon-1 mutant huntingtin transgenic mouse model; RNS, reactive nitrogen species; ROS, reactive oxygen species; SMOX, spermine oxidase; SMS, spermine synthase; SNpc, substantia nigra pars compacta; SOD1, superoxide dismutase 1; SOD1^{G93A}, G93A mutant superoxide dismutase 1 transgenic mouse model of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; Spd, spermidine; Spm, spermine; SRM, spermidine synthase; UT-B, urea transporter B; YAC128Q, yeast artificial chromosome Huntington's disease mouse model (128 CAG repeats)

Introduction

Neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's (AD), Parkinson's (PD), Huntington's disease (HD), and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) involve complex metabolic disturbances, and recent clinical and experimental data demonstrate that neurodegenerative and metabolic diseases display coexisting metabolic dysfunctions [1]. Emerging evidences implicate dysregulation of arginine (Arg) metabolism as a contributing factor in neurodegeneration. Arg is a semi-essential amino acid with a versatile metabolic profile – it serves not only as a building block for proteins, but also as precursor for numerous bioactive molecules [2]. In the central nervous system (CNS), Arg metabolism intersects with pathways of neurotransmission, neurovascular regulation, mitochondrial homeostasis, intracellular signalling, immune response and many others – processes that are impaired during the progression of neurodegenerative diseases. Arginase, by regulating Arg flux through its conversion to ornithine (Orn) and urea, has emerged as a significant regulator of these pathways, shifting Arg utilization away from nitric oxide (NO) synthesis toward the production of Orn-derived metabolites. Of two arginase isoenzymes present in mammalian tissues, the role of Arg1 is better recognized, especially in liver, where it is involved in ammonia detoxification as a part of urea cycle and in immune system/microglia, where it participates in inflammatory signalling and polarization of macrophages and microglia towards alternative, M2-type, phenotype. Meanwhile the role of Arg2, as well as other tissue-expressed Arg1 is still not fully understood. Alterations in arginase isoenzymes has been observed in aging and in several pathological conditions, ranging from cardiovascular and metabolic disorders, cancer as well as neurodegenerative diseases, suggesting that arginase may be a common mediator of disease-related metabolic imbalance [3]. In this review, we integrate disease-specific changes in arginase isoenzymes and related metabolic pathways identified in biospecimens and post-mortem tissues derived from patients and disease models with mechanistic findings from the experimental systems to provide an overview of arginase involvement in the pathogenesis of common neurodegenerative disorders. We also discuss possible therapeutic strategies targeting this pathway and outline directions for future studies to better understand the isoenzyme-, tissue- and cell type-specific, and disease stage-dependent consequences of arginase dysregulation, with the aim of designing mechanism-based therapies against neurodegenerative conditions.

Cellular Arg homeostasis

Arg sources and metabolism in the brain. Unlike the liver, the healthy brain lacks a complete urea cycle, as two of its enzymes – carbamoyl phosphate synthetase (CPS) and Orn transcarbamylase (OTC) – are present only at minimal levels in this tissue [4–6] (Figure 1). Consequently, the brain relies on peripheral Arg supply, protein turnover and metabolic recycling rather than *de novo* synthesis. Systemic Arg availability depends on mitochondrial citrulline (Cit) synthesis in the small intestine from dietary glutamate (Glu) and glutamine (Gln), followed by conversion of circulating Cit to Arg primarily the kidneys [7,8]. Arg crosses the blood–brain barrier (BBB) and is actively shuttled between brain cells.

Figure 1. Arginase at the crossroads of Arg metabolism in the brain. By regulating the cellular balance between Arg and Orn, arginase controls multiple critical metabolic pathways in the brain, including the synthesis of NO, Cre, Pro, Glu/Gln/α-KG, GABA, and polyamines. In addition, arginase participates in the urea cycle, which can be activated in brain pathologies, such as AD. Abbreviations: 3-APA – 3-aminopropanal, α-KG – α-ketoglutarate, ABALDH – γ-aminobutyraldehyde dehydrogenase, AD – Alzheimer’s disease, ADC – arginine decarboxylase, AGAT – arginine:glycine amidinotransferase, Agm – agmatine, AGMAT – agmatinase, ARG – arginase, Arg – arginine, AS – argininosuccinate, ASL – argininosuccinate lyase, Asp – aspartate, ASS – argininosuccinate synthetase, ATP – adenosine triphosphate, Cit – citrulline, CK – creatine kinase, CP – carbamoyl phosphate, CPS – carbamoyl phosphate synthetase, Cre – creatine, Cre – creatine, DAO – diamine oxidase, Fum – fumarate, GAA – guanidinoacetate, GABA – γ-aminobutyric acid, GABAL – γ-aminobutyraldehyde, GAD – glutamate decarboxylase, GAMT – guanidinoacetate methyltransferase, GDH – glutamate dehydrogenase, Gln – glutamine, GLS – glutaminase, Glu – glutamate, Gly – glycine, GS – glutamine synthetase, GSA – glutamate-γ-semialdehyde, MAO-B – monoamine oxidase B, N-AcGABA – N-acetyl-γ-aminobutyric acid, N-AcGABAL – N-acetyl-γ-aminobutyraldehyde, N-AcPut – N-acetylputrescine, N-AcSpd – N-acetylspermidine, N-AcSpm – N-acetylspermine, NO – nitric oxide, NOS – nitric oxide synthase, OAT – ornithine aminotransferase, ODC – ornithine decarboxylase, Orn – ornithine, Orn – ornithine, OTC – ornithine transcarbamylase, P5C – pyrroline-5-carboxylate, P5CD – pyrroline-5-carboxylate dehydrogenase, P5CR – pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase, P5CS – pyrroline-5-carboxylate synthase, PAO – polyamine oxidase, PAT – putrescine aminotransferase-like activity, P-Cre – phosphocreatine, PO – proline oxidase, Pro – proline, Put – putrescine, SMOX – spermine oxidase, SMS – spermine synthase, Spd – spermidine, Spm – spermine, SRM – spermidine synthase, SSAT – spermidine/spermine N¹-acetyltransferase.

The major recycling route in the brain is the Cit–NO cycle: neuronal and endothelial NO synthases (NOS; nNOS and eNOS) convert Arg to NO and Cit, which is recycled back to Arg by argininosuccinate synthase (ASS) and argininosuccinate lyase (ASL) [9]. Since Arg availability is a rate-limiting factor for NO synthesis, arginase influences NO homeostasis by competing with NOS for Arg [10] (Figure 1).

Beyond regulating NO production, brain arginase primarily controls polyamine synthesis, supplying Orn for Orn decarboxylase (ODC), the first and rate-limiting enzyme of the canonical, cytosolic polyamine synthesis pathway leading to the production of putrescine (Put), spermidine (Spd) and spermine (Spm) [11]. Arginase can also affect Arg availability for astrocytic arginine decarboxylase (ADC), which produces agmatine (Agm) [12], a neuroactive metabolite and a minor source for polyamines, as Agm can be converted to Put by mitochondrial enzyme, agmatinase, although this pathway is less efficient than ODC pathway [13] (Figure 1). Polyamines occur at millimolar concentrations in mammalian cells [14], and the brain exhibits exceptionally high spermine synthase (SMS) activity relative to spermidine synthase (SRM), a feature unique among mammalian tissues [15], underscoring the importance of Spm for CNS. The polyamine pathway may also participate in γ -butyric acid (GABA) production, as Put can be deaminated via pathways involving either diamine oxidase or monoamine oxidase B (MAO-B), supporting GABA synthesis in astrocytes and astrocytic modulation of GABA-ergic neurotransmission [16] (Figure 1).

Orn can also be metabolized by Orn aminotransferase (OAT), a bidirectional mitochondrial enzyme interconverting Orn and pyrroline-5-carboxylate (P5C) [17], a precursor for Glu and proline (Pro) [18], and arginase can affect both Pro and Glu levels in cell [19] (Figure 1). In the adult rodent brain, Pro synthesis from Orn is well documented [20–22], while Pro-derived P5C predominantly is used as a Glu precursor [23,24].

Importantly, Orn can be generated through arginase-independent pathways. In *Arg2*^{-/-} mouse striatum, two alternative Orn sources have been proposed: Pro→Orn pathway and arginine:glycine amidinotransferase (AGAT)-mediated Arg to Orn conversion underscored by elevated levels of OAT and AGAT [25]. Consistently, increased guanidinoacetate (GAA), a byproduct of AGAT activity is detected in *Arg1*-deficient patients [26] and animal models of *Arg1* and *Arg2* deficiency [27,28]. AGAT initiates creatine (Cre) synthesis, another major pathway of Arg utilization, accounting for ~30% of whole-body Arg usage [29] (Figure 1).

Together, these pathways highlight both the metabolic versatility of Arg in the brain, and the central role of arginase in coordinating its utilization, however the allocation of Arg among protein synthesis and competing metabolic pathways across CNS cell types remains poorly understood.

Transport of Arg and its metabolites. Arg guanidinium group has a very high pKa (~13.8), rendering Arg positively charged at physiological pH [30] and impermeable to lipid membranes [31]. Consequently, intracellular and intercellular Arg movement relies on cationic amino acid transporters. At the BBB, astrocytes and endothelial cells import circulating Arg via system y⁺ transporters, primarily cationic amino acid transporter 1 (CAT1), supplying the brain interstitial space [32,33]. In the CNS, Arg recycling is tightly coupled to intercellular transport. Although NOS (particularly nNOS), ASS and ASL are all predominantly neuronal they are rarely expressed within the same neuronal subpopulations in the healthy brain [34–37]. As a result, efficient Arg regeneration (and NO production) requires active Arg and Cit exchange between cells [9].

Intercellular transport is similarly essential for cerebral polyamine homeostasis, as their metabolism and storage are highly compartmentalized. Because polyamines cross BBB only minimally [38,39], the brain depends on local Arg and Orn availability rather than circulating polyamines, unlike peripheral tissues. Astrocytes are considered the primary polyamine storage site [40], whereas the major biosynthetic enzymes, ODC, SRM and SMS, are predominantly neuronal [41,42], implying that astrocytic uptake follows neuronal synthesis.

In addition, nitrogenous waste products, generated from Arg metabolism are removed via dedicated transporters; intracellular urea is exported through urea transporter B (UT-B), identified as the primary cerebral urea transporter [43,44]

These observations demonstrate that Arg metabolism in the brain is integrated with transporter-mediated trafficking of Arg and its metabolites across cellular compartments.

Arginase isoenzymes and their compartmentalization. Mammals express two arginase isoenzymes encoded by distinct genes with ~60% sequence homology, both being homotrimeric, Mn²⁺-dependent metalloenzymes [45,46]. Arg1 is a cytosolic enzyme, best known from its involvement in the urea cycle [47], whereas Arg2, also encoded by a nuclear gene, is synthesized as a mitochondrial preprotein and processed into a stable active enzyme following mitochondrial import [48]. Arg2 is highly expressed in kidney, but present also in several other organs, including pancreas, prostate, vasculature and immune system [49].

In the CNS, both isoenzymes are expressed, but their localization remains debated. In rodent brain, immunostaining-based analyses demonstrated the presence of Arg1 and Arg2 in neuronal cells in selected regions [50,51], while *in situ* hybridization showed broad, largely neuron-specific expression of both mRNAs, often within the same neuronal populations [52]. An exception was initially reported in the striatum, where Arg1 expression was limited to a small neuronal subset and Arg2 expression either absent or markedly reduced [52]. However, later studies have yielded different results: in rats, Arg2 mRNA displayed a diffuse brain-wide, neuronal and glial distribution, with relatively higher expression in the striatum [34], whereas Arg1 protein remained neuron-specific [53]. In humans, Arg2 mRNA appears to be broadly distributed, with high expression in the caudate nucleus and putamen [54]. These discrepancies likely reflect differences in species, brain regions, and experimental approaches.

Recent evidences converge on the striatum as a uniquely Arg2-enriched brain region. qPCR and immunoblotting identify the mouse striatum as Arg1-depleted and Arg2-rich [55]. Striatal Arg2 localizes predominantly to medium spiny neurons (MSNs) [28], consistent with earlier translational profiling identifying Arg2 as one of the most distinctive transcripts in dopamine (DA) D2 receptor-expressing MSNs compared with other brain cells [56]. In addition, Arg2 has been found as predominant arginase isoenzyme in the human frontal cortex [57]. It therefore appears, that Arg2 is the major cerebral arginase isoenzyme, with variable expression across brain regions.

Subcellular compartmentalization of arginase isoenzymes may potentially influence Orn fate. Cytosolic Arg1-derived Orn would be expected to be preferentially available for cytosolic ODC, supporting polyamine synthesis, whereas mitochondrial Arg2-derived Orn could feed Pro and Glu synthesis through mitochondrial OAT. However, this is oversimplified, due to active Orn transport across mitochondrial membrane [58]. Consistently, Arg2 deficiency

alters polyamine homeostasis. In Arg2 deficient striatum, Put loss and Spm accumulation is observed, demonstrating significant involvement of Arg2 in polyamine synthesis [25].

Preservation of Orn emerges as a consistent compensatory response to Arg2 alterations. In Arg2^{-/-} mice, Orn concentrations remain stable across tissues despite substantial Arg accumulation [59–62]. Consistently, neuron-specific Arg2 overexpression lowers Arg without affecting Orn, whereas Arg1 overexpression increases Orn [63], indicating isoenzyme-specific control of Orn pools. These findings support the existence of discrete subcellular Arg and/or Orn pools, with the Arg2-associated pool being efficiently buffered.

Beyond polyamines, Arg2 loss affects broader Arg metabolism. Metabolomic study identified GAA, Cre and creatinine as key discriminant metabolites in the striatum following Arg2 deletion, with enrichment of pathways related to urea cycle disorders, amino group metabolism and Cre synthesis [28], underscoring Arg2 role in coordinating nitrogen and energy metabolism in striatal neurons.

Finally, although Arg2 is classically mitochondrial, its distribution is dynamic. Its overactivation may be linked with its translocation to the cytosol in specific conditions [64]. Cytosolic localization of Arg2 correlated with increased arginase activity has been reported in hippocampal neurons in an AD mouse model [50], suggesting that pathological conditions may further modify Arg2 compartmentalization and function in the brain.

Disease-specific alterations in Arg metabolites

Recent findings provide accumulating evidences that neurological disorders, including neurodegenerative disease exhibit distinctive changes in Arg and its downstream metabolites, reflecting alterations in enzymatic pathways controlled by arginase. Below we summarize key metabolite alterations reported in major neurodegenerative diseases and their experimental models.

AD. Increasing evidence implicates metabolic dysregulation in AD [65,66], including disturbances in Arg pathways [67,68]. Human data on circulating Arg are, however, inconsistent: plasma/serum Arg has been reported as decreased or increased, with several studies showing poor correlation between peripheral Arg and clinical status (Table 1). A better correlation is observed in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), where Arg levels are increased in AD compared with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) patients (Table 1), suggesting relationship between Arg content and disease stage. *Post-mortem* brain studies reveal region-dependence of Arg alterations: while Arg levels were reduced in the temporal cortex, they were elevated in the hippocampus and superior frontal gyrus (SFG) of AD patients (Table 1), suggesting that significantly differential regional consumption and/or replenishment of Arg may be responsible for poor correlation between biofluid Arg levels and the disease.

Experimental models recapitulate this heterogeneity. Arg metabolism has been found to be altered in the urine of APP (amyloid- β (A β) precursor protein)/PS1 (presenilin 1) double mutant mice at presymptomatic stage (Table 1). In CVN-AD mice (APP quadruple mutant model on inducible NOS (iNOS)-null background), brain Arg loss was reported to spatially correlate with A β accumulation and neuronal injury, whereas in A β -infused rats, Arg levels didn't change significantly and in the brain of frontotemporal dementia (FTD) model, PS19 mice, Arg was found to increase in several regions at late stage of the disease (Table 1).

Collectively, these perturbations appear to reflect tissue-, stage- and model-dependent cellular status of Arg metabolism, rather than uniform disease-related pattern.

Metabolomic studies more consistently indicate reduced Orn in AD tissues. Orn was decreased in AD patients serum, and numerous regions in *post-mortem* brain tissue from AD and FTD patients (Table 1). Notably, Orn depletion can occur despite arginase activation, suggesting parallel involvement of Orn-utilizing pathways. Indeed, it was proposed that concurrent upregulation of arginase, ODC, and OTC in AD accelerates substrate flux, producing relative Orn deficiency despite increased production capacity [5,69].

In contrast to Orn, levels of the second arginase product, urea, have recently been consistently shown to be increased in AD. *Post-mortem* metabolomics revealed striking urea elevation across AD brain regions, with the highest increases in most affected regions – hippocampus and entorhinal cortex (ECx) (6.5- and 5.6-fold), and substantial elevations in moderately affected regions and in relatively spared cerebellum (4.9–5.3-fold) (Table 1). Additional studies confirm altered urea cycle-related metabolism in AD [70,71]. AD patients also show excess ammonia in CSF (Table 1), further reinforcing the concept of disrupted nitrogen handling.

Evidence linking the NO pathway to AD is substantial but inconsistent. Many studies report reduced NO production reflected by decreased CSF nitrite/nitrate (NO_x) levels correlated with cognitive decline (Table 1), decreased NOS activity paralleled by nNOS, eNOS and iNOS expression loss in SFG and hippocampus [72], and reduced Cit which can reflect reduced NO (Table 1). However, reported alterations in NOS isoform expression [73] and NO production in AD vary widely across studies (Table 1). Thus, NO signalling in AD appears to be determined by regional vascular, inflammatory, and neuronal states rather than a directional change.

Polyamine metabolism represents another pathway commonly affected in AD. *Post-mortem* brain metabolomics links AD pathology to altered Orn-derived metabolites and ODC-associated flux [74], while single-cell transcriptomic analysis point to astrocytic polyamine biosynthesis as a pathway associated with greater resilience to neuropathology and cognitive decline in AD patients [75]. Increased Spd levels were observed in temporal cortex, whereas reduced Spd was found in SFG, and increased Spm in hippocampus (Table 1). Put levels were usually shown to decline in affected regions (Table 1). Finally, comparative *post-mortem* metabolomics identified a shared polyamine stress response in AD and progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP), suggesting a common tauopathy-related polyamine pattern [76]. Increase in Spd was also observed in the serum of MCI patients, with a trend toward higher levels in AD, indicating that Spd levels are altered early in the AD disease course (Table 1). Model systems further support polyamine involvement, showing elevation in Spd and Put across different regions (Table 1). In contrast, data on Spm levels are less consistent and model-dependent, with increases reported in APP/PS1 mice and decreases observed in PS19 mice (Table 1). These findings support a context-dependent polyamine stress response rather than patterned individual polyamine gain or loss.

Agm changes in AD are similarly age- and region-dependent. Some studies report no AD-specific Agm changes, but instead region-dependent age-related decline [72]. Others, however, report disease-associated loss, such as the study by Mein and colleagues showing decreased Agm in the hippocampus of AD and FTD subjects (Table 1). Consistently, intracerebroventricular administration of A β reduced Agm levels in mouse hippocampus and

prefrontal cortex (Table 1). In contrast, Agm levels were reported to remain unchanged in PS19 mouse brain [77].

A less explored aspect of Arg metabolism in AD is the contribution of toxic byproducts of polyamine turnover. Elevated levels of the reactive aldehyde acrolein, a potent contributor to AD pathogenesis [78,79], have been detected in AD brain tissue, particularly in hippocampus and amygdala, where it colocalizes with neurofibrillary tangles and dystrophic neurites surrounding amyloid plaques (Table 1). While lipid peroxidation represents the major endogenous source of acrolein, enzymatic oxidation of polyamines may constitute an important contributor in the brain, particularly under conditions of altered polyamine metabolism.

In summary, arginase involvement in AD, through modulation of Arg to Orn conversion rates, may converge on three key features: impaired nitrogen disposal with ammonia and urea accumulation, inconsistent but meaningful perturbation of NO pathway, and dysregulation of polyamine homeostasis that may be maladaptive or protective. Apparent discrepancies across regions and disease stages likely reflect differences in cellular composition and the metabolic networks engaged as pathology evolves.

metabolite	subject	biospecimen	alterations	details	reference
Arg	AD patients	plasma	↓	AD vs CS	[80]
	AD patients	plasma	↓	MCI vs CS, AD vs CS	[81]
	AD patients	serum	↓	AD vs CS	[82]
	AD patients	serum	↓	dementia vs CS	[83]
	AD patients	plasma	↑	MCI vs CS, AD vs CS	[84]
	AD patients	plasma	↑	MCI vs CS, pre-AD MCI vs MCI	[85]
	AD patients	CSF	↑	AD vs MCI	[86]
	AD patients	CSF	↓	MCI vs CS	[81]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	TCx; AD vs CS	[87]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	SFG, Hip; AD vs CS	[72]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	SFG, Hip; AD vs CS, FTD vs CS	[88]
	CVN-AD mice	brain	↓	spatial correlation with neuropathology	[89]
	APP/PS1 mice	brain	↑	FCx, Hip; late stage	[90]
	PS19 mice	brain	↑	Hip, Cb; late stage	[77]
	PS19 mice	brain	↑	Hip, PHR, St; late stage	[91]
Orn	AD patients	serum	↓	AD vs CS	[92]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	SFG, Hip, Cb; AD vs CS	[72]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Hip, ECx, Cb; AD vs CS	[93]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Hip, FCx, TCx; AD vs CS	[88]
	FTD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Hip, FCx, TCx; FTD vs CS	[88]
urea	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	Hip, ECx, MTG, SCx, MCx, CG, Cb; AD vs CS	[93]
ammonia	AD patients	CSF	↑	AD vs MCI	[86]
NO-derived species	AD patients	plasma	↓	NOx; AD vs CS	[94]
	AD patients	CSF	↓	NOx; AD vs CS	[95]
	AD patients	CSF	↓	NO ₃ ⁻ ; correlation with cognitive impairment; AD vs CS	[96]
	AD patients	CSF	↑	NOx; AD vs CS	[97]
Cit	AD patients	serum	↓	dementia vs CS	[83]
Put	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	FL, PL; AD vs CS	[74]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	TCx; AD vs CS	[98]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	SFG, Hip, Cb; AD vs CS	[72]

	PS19 mice	brain	↑	FCx, Hip, PHR, St, Cb	[91]
	MCI patients	serum	↑	MCI vs CS	[99]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Cb; AD vs CS	[76]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	SFG; AD vs CS	[72]
Spd	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	TCx; AD vs CS	[98]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	FL, PL; AD vs CS	[74]
	APP/PS1 mice	brain	↑	FCx, Hip, PHR, Cb; late stage	[90]
	PS19 mice	brain	↑	FCx, Hip, PHR, St	[91]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Cb; AD vs CS	[76]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	FL, PL; AD vs CS	[74]
Spm	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	Hip; AD vs CS	[72]
	APP/PS1 mice	brain	↑	FCx, Hip, PHR; late stage	[90]
	PS19 mice	brain	↓	Hip, PHR	[91]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Hip; FTD vs CS	[88]
Agm	FTD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Hip; FTD vs CS	[88]
	A β -infused mice	brain	↓	Hip, PFCx	[100]
acrolein	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	Hip; spatial correlation with neuropathology; AD vs CS	[101]
	AD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	Amy, Hip; AD vs CS	[102]

Table 1. Summary of metabolite alterations in arginase-related metabolic pathways in AD. Abbreviations: A β , amyloid β ; AD, Alzheimer's disease; Agm, agmatine; Amy, amygdala; APP/PS1, amyloid precursor protein/presenilin-1 transgenic Alzheimer's disease mouse model; Arg, arginine; Cb, cerebellum; CG, cingulate gyrus; Cit, citrulline; CS, control subjects; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; CVN-AD; APP quadruple mutant Alzheimer's disease mouse model on inducible nitric oxide synthase-null background; ECx, entorhinal cortex; FCx, frontal cortex; FL, frontal lobe; FTD, frontotemporal dementia; Hip, hippocampus; MCI, mild cognitive impairment; MCx, motor cortex MTG, middle temporal gyrus; NO, nitric oxide; NOx, nitrates + nitrites; Orn, ornithine; PFCx, prefrontal cortex; PHR, parahippocampal region; PL, parietal lobe; PS19, P301S tau transgenic mouse model; Put, putrescine; SCx, sensory cortex; SFG, superior frontal gyrus; Spd, spermidine; Spm, spermine; St, striatum; TCx, temporal cortex

PD. In PD patients, Orn alterations have been reported, particularly in blood. Plasma Orn increases progressively from healthy controls to early-stage PD, reaching the highest levels in advanced disease, suggesting stage-dependent dysregulation (Table 2). Similarly to AD, urea levels are significantly increased in the PD patient blood as well as in 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP)-exposed mouse brain, particularly in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) and the striatum (Table 2).

CSF NO_x levels are most often unchanged in PD [103–105], although increases have been reported in some studies (Table 2). Also, in *post-mortem* brains of PD patients, protein nitrosylation has been observed specifically in the SNpc (Table 2), suggesting that disrupted NO handling may be local and not necessarily reflected in biofluids.

Evidence for altered polyamine metabolism in PD is mixed and compartment-specific. In CSF, higher total polyamines, increased Put and reduced Spd have been reported (Table 2), consistent with impaired Put-to-Spd conversion by SRM. Additionally, longitudinal analyses indicate that polyamines rise in serum as PD progresses (Table 2), in line with stage-dependent elevation of Orn. Importantly, serum levels of Put degradation metabolite, N-acetylputrescine predicted clinical worsening in a subgroup characterized by gait and postural instability, supporting polyamine-related metabolites as candidate biomarkers for PD progression [106]. In contrast, post-mortem basal ganglia tissue shows no significant changes in total polyamine content [107], suggesting systemic rather than localized alterations.

Similarly to AD, PD brains show evidence of enhanced polyamine oxidation. Spm oxidase (SMOX) expression is elevated in PD brains [108], and accordingly, levels of acrolein are increased in the SNpc of PD patients (Table 2).

Overall, PD is characterized by progressive dysregulation of peripheral Orn and polyamine metabolism, largely stable CSF NO end-products, and brain evidence linking polyamines metabolism to acrolein-related toxicity through enhanced SMOX activity.

metabolite	subject	biospecimen	alterations	details	reference
Orn	PD patients	plasma	↑	correlation with disease stage; late stage PD vs early stage PD vs CS	[109]
urea	PD patients	serum	↑	PD vs CS	[110]
	MPTP mice	brain	↑	SNpc, St	[110]/
NO-derived species	PD patients	CSF	↑	NO ₃ ⁻ ; PD vs CS	[111]
	PD patients	CSF	↑	NOx; PD vs CS	[97]
	PD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	nitrosyl hemoglobin; SNpc; PD vs CS	[106]
polyamines total	PD patients	serum	↑	correlation with disease progression	[112]
Put	PD patients	CSF	↑	PD vs CS	[113]
Spd	PD patients	CSF	↓	PD vs CS	[113]
acrolein	PD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	PD vs CS; acrolein-modified αSyn	[114]

Table 2. Summary of metabolite alterations in arginase-related metabolic pathways in PD. Abbreviations: αSyn, α-synuclein; CS, control subjects; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; MPTP, 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine; NO, nitric oxide; NOx, nitrates + nitrites; Orn, ornithine; PD, Parkinson's disease; Put, putrescine; SNpc, substantia nigra pars compacta; Spd, spermidine; St, striatum

HD. Although Arg and its direct amino acid products (Cit and Orn) were found to be unaltered in CSF across disease stages, from presymptomatic to late HD [115], Orn and Pro were significantly decreased in affected regions of *post-mortem* brains, particularly the putamen, while Cit was increased in the blood of symptomatic patients (Table 3). In animal models, Arg and Cit (but not Orn) were increased in the plasma from a transgenic HD sheep model at the presymptomatic stage, as well as in the striatum of the YAC128Q mouse model, expressing full-length human huntingtin (HTT) with 128 glutamine repeats, also at the presymptomatic stage, where increase included Orn as well (Table 3). In addition, a progressive increase in Cit levels was observed in the blood of two other mouse HD models, R6/2 and Hdh^{(CAG)¹⁵⁰}, and closely paralleled disease progression within each line (Table 3).

Similar to AD, CSF urea is significantly increased in HD; although only at the late stage (Table 3). Widespread urea elevation is also present in *post-mortem* brains, including both more (putamen, globus pallidus, motor cortex) and less (cerebellum, sensory cortex) affected regions (Table 3). This was confirmed in larger cohorts (cerebellum and superior frontal gyrus), where urea elevation was already found at presymptomatic stage (Table 3). Model studies confirmed these findings, as increased urea levels were observed in the plasma and the striatum (but not other analysed regions) of presymptomatic transgenic HD sheep (Table 3). These findings suggest an early and progressive dysregulation of Arg→urea metabolism, potentially contributing to disease pathogenesis.

Elevated NO_x levels have been observed in CSF of HD patients (Table 3), although evidence for disrupted NO homeostasis comes largely from mouse models. R6/2 mice show decreased NO activity, consistent with reduced nNOS protein levels in the striatum and cortex [116]. In contrast, elevated 3-nitrotyrosine (3-NT), a marker of peroxynitrite-mediated protein modification, was reported in the same and another study (Table 3), the latter also showing increased iNOS expression [117]. Notably, dietary Arg enrichment accelerated striatal neuropathology and motor impairment and increased brain 3-NT in R6/1 HD mice [118], linking Arg availability to nitrosative stress and disease progression.

Human data on polyamines are limited - Spm was found to be reduced in HD putamen (Table 3). Additional support comes from SMS G56S mutant mice, a model of Snyder-Robinson syndrome, where severe polyamine imbalance leads to motor phenotypes and HD-related signalling is identified as a strongly enriched pathway in the brain of mutant animals [119], suggesting polyamine involvement in HD pathogenesis.

Overall, Arg and urea accumulation, nitrosative stress and polyamine imbalance suggests broad remodelling of Arg-related metabolic pathways in HD. The prominence of urea, suggests that arginase-mediated urea generation may represent a mechanism significantly contributing to disease pathogenesis.

metabolite	subject	biospecimen	alterations	details	reference
Arg	tg HD sheep	plasma	↑	presymptomatic stage	[120]
	YAC128Q mice	brain	↑	St; presymptomatic stage	[55]
Orn	HD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Ptm, GP, Hip; HD vs CS	[121]
	YAC128Q mice	brain	↑	St; presymptomatic stage	[55]
urea	HD patients	CSF	↑	HD vs CS; late stage	[115]
	HD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	SFG, Cb; HD vs CS; from presymptomatic stage	[122]
	HD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	Ptm, GP, SN, Cb, Hip, MTG, CG, SCx, MCx, MFG, ECx; HD vs CS	[121]
	HD patients	post-mortem brain	↑	Ptm, GP, SN, Cb, Hip, MTG, CG, SCx, MCx, MFG, ECx; HD vs CS	[121]
	tg HD sheep	plasma	↑	presymptomatic stage	[120]
	tg HD sheep	brain	↑	St; presymptomatic stage	[122]
Pro	HD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Ptm, SCx, Cb, Hip; HD vs CS	[121]
NO-derived species	HD patients	CSF	↑	NOx; HD vs CS	[97]
	R6/2 mice	brain	↑	3-NT; Cb	[115]
	R6/2 mice	brain	↑	3-NT; Cx	[122]
Cit	HD patients	serum	↑	HD vs CS	[123]
	tg HD sheep	plasma	↑	presymptomatic stage	[120]/
	YAC128Q mice	brain	↑	St; presymptomatic stage	[55]
	R6/2 mice	serum	↑	correlation with disease progression	[123]
	Hdh ^{(CAG)¹⁵⁰} mice	serum	↑	correlation with disease progression	[123]
Spm	HD patients	post-mortem brain	↓	Ptm; HD vs CS	[107]

Table 3. Summary of metabolite alterations in arginase-related metabolic pathways in HD. Abbreviations: 3-NT, 3-nitrotyrosine; Arg, arginine; Cb, cerebellum; CG, cingulate gyrus; Cit, citrulline; CS, control subjects; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; Cx, cortex; ECx, entorhinal cortex; GP, globus pallidus; HD, Huntington's disease; Hdh^{(CAG)¹⁵⁰}, knock-in Huntington's disease mouse model with 150 CAG repeat huntingtin; Hip, hippocampus; MCx, motor cortex; MFG, middle frontal gyrus; MTG, middle temporal gyrus; NO, nitric oxide; NOx, nitrates + nitrites; Orn, ornithine; Pro, proline; Ptm, putamen; R6/2, exon-1 mutant huntingtin transgenic mouse model; SCx, sensory cortex; SFG, superior frontal gyrus; SN, substantia nigra; Spm, spermine; St, striatum; tg, transgenic; YAC128Q, yeast artificial chromosome Huntington's disease mouse model (128 CAG repeats)

ALS. Direct measurements of Arg levels in ALS patients biofluids or *post-mortem* tissue are limited, thus human evidence for Arg pathway involvement largely derives from downstream readouts, particularly NO and nitrosative stress. Multiple studies report elevated NO-related metabolites in patient biofluids, implicating enhanced Arg utilization in NOS pathways (Table 4). In parallel, free 3-NT is significantly increased in CSF from sporadic ALS patients and *post-mortem* spinal cord tissue from both sporadic and familial ALS cases (Table 4), predominantly in neurons but also in astrocytes [124,125]. Animal models substantially reproduce these findings: increased 3-NT in spinal cord of superoxide dismutase 1 (SOD1) mutant G37R and G93A mouse lines (Table 4). Importantly, in the presymptomatic SOD1^{G93A} model, protein nitration found in motor neurons suggests a pathogenic role rather than a terminal effect (Table 4).

Experimental models provide more direct insight into Arg homeostasis dysregulation: metabolic profiling of symptomatic SOD1^{G93A} mice identified Arg pathway in cortex, together with Pro metabolism, as a strong discriminator from control animals, indicating major reprogramming during disease progression [126]. At the cellular level, mutant SOD1 motor neuron-like cells show impaired Arg uptake via system y⁺ [127].

Evidence for polyamine dysregulation in ALS patients is limited. *Post-mortem* spinal cord exhibited no major changes in Put, Spd or Spm across spinal cord structures, except elevated Spd and Spm in the ventral horn of female patients, indicating possible sex- and region-specific alteration (Table 4). In contrast, ALS models demonstrate a more pronounced changes: SOD1^{G93A} mice exhibit increased ODC activity and elevated Put in affected spinal cord and brain regions at symptomatic stages (Table 4), with relative preservation of unaffected structures, such as cerebellum and fronto-parietal cortex [128], indicating an association between polyamine dysregulation and neuronal loss. Histological analyses reveal loss of Spd/Spm immunoreactivity in surviving lumbar motor neurons in this model (Table 4). Polyamine dysregulation also extends to the periphery: in SOD1^{G93A} mice, polyamine metabolism emerges as one of the major dysregulated pathways in ALS-affected skeletal muscles [129], suggesting polyamine imbalance as a systemic feature of ALS models.

Collectively, ALS features robust dysregulation of Arg-dependent NO pathways and resulting nitrosative stress in patients and models. Modest polyamine dysregulation is detected in human spinal cord, being more pronounced in models, where it is tightly associated with neurodegeneration and extends to muscle. These findings highlight Arg metabolism as a significant metabolic contributor to ALS pathogenesis.

In summary, across neurodegenerative diseases, Arg metabolism shows heterogeneous, context-dependent alterations. In AD, the most robust signature is arginase-linked nitrogen dysregulation, with widespread urea accumulation, impaired ammonia handling, and consistent Orn loss, while NO and individual polyamines vary by region and stage. PD is characterized by progressive peripheral Orn changes and disrupted polyamine handling, with relatively stable central NO but clear evidence of polyamine oxidation-related toxicity. HD shows a particularly consistent Arg→urea phenotype, with region-specific Orn depletion and early and progressive brain urea elevation, nitrosative stress in models, and polyamine imbalance. In ALS, altered Arg utilization manifests mainly as increased NO production and excessive nitrosative stress, accompanied by polyamine dysregulation prominent in models and peripheral tissues. Overall, these patterns highlight Arg pathways as key determinants of pathogenesis with biomarker and therapeutic relevance.

metabolite	subject	biospecimen	alterations	details	reference
NO-derived species	ALS patients	CSF	↑	NOx; sporadic ALS vs CS	[97]
	ALS patients	CSF	↑	NOx; sporadic ALS vs CS	[130]
	ALS patients	CSF	↑	NOx; sporadic ALS vs CS	[131]
	ALS patients	CSF	↑	3-NT; sporadic ALS vs CS	[132]
	ALS patients	post-mortem SC	↑	3-NT; sporadic ALS vs CS	[133]
	ALS patients	post-mortem SC	↑	3-NT; sporadic and familial ALS vs CS	[124]
	SOD1 ^{G37R} mice	brain, SC	↑	3-NT; BS, SC; from early stage	[134]
	SOD1 ^{G93A} mice	brain, SC	↑	3-NT; Ctx, upper and lower SC	[135]
	SOD1 ^{G93A} mice	SC	↑	protein nitration; SC; from presymptomatic stage	[136]
Put	SOD1 ^{G37R} mice	brain, SC	↑	BS, cervical and lumbar SC; symptomatic stage	[128]
Spd	ALS patients	post-mortem SC	↑	ventral horn; ALS vs CS; only in females	[137]
Spm	ALS patients	post-mortem SC	↑	ventral horn; ALS vs CS; only in females	[137]
	SOD1 ^{G37R} mice	SC	↓	lumbar SC; Spd/Spm immunoreactivity in motor neurons	[138]

Table 4. Summary of metabolite alterations in arginase-related metabolic pathways in ALS. Abbreviations: 3-NT; 3-nitrotyrosine; ALS, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; BS, brainstem; CS, control subjects; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; NO, nitric oxide; NOx, nitrates + nitrites; Put, putrescine; SC, spinal cord; SOD1^{G37R}, G37R mutant superoxide dismutase 1 transgenic mouse model of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; SOD1^{G93A}, G93A mutant superoxide dismutase 1 transgenic mouse model of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; Spd, spermidine; Spm, spermine

Arginase alterations across neurodegenerative disorders

Consistent with Arg metabolic dyshomeostasis, diverse lines of evidence across different disorders point to arginase alteration as a feature of neurodegeneration. Here, we detail disease-specific changes in Arg1/Arg2 expression or activity.

AD. Converging findings indicate altered arginase expression and activity in AD brain, implicating dysregulated Arg→Orn metabolism in pathogenesis. A rare Arg2 allele (rs742869) is associated with increased AD risk and earlier onset, particularly in men [69]. Consistently, Arg2 mRNA [69] and protein [72] as well as Arg1 mRNA [139] are elevated in *post-mortem* AD brains, with increased arginase activity in disease-affected regions [72]. IN SFG and hippocampus, elevated activity is largely attributable to Arg2 and inversely correlates with NOS activity, indicating Arg2-associated shift towards Arg catabolism [72]. Although evidence for arginase upregulation is largely consistent, single studies report different results, for example transcriptomic analysis of AD hippocampi identified reduced Arg2 mRNA [140]. Such discrepancies likely reflect cell-type specificity and differences in disease stage, region and methodology.

Experimental models support an elevated arginase profile. Transcriptomic profiling of whole-brain lysates from CVN-AD mice showed early, transient upregulation of ARG1 and other immune-suppressive genes prior to overt neuronal loss, implicating arginase induction in an early disease phase characterized by immune polarization towards M2 phenotype [89]. CD11c⁺-microglia-derived extracellular Arg1 was enriched in regions of A β accumulation and neuronal injury in this model [89], whereas Arg2 localized predominantly to neuronal cell bodies in APP/PS1/tau mutant triple transgenic mice (3xTg) [50], suggesting isoenzyme-specific compartmentalization. An independent study confirmed that Arg1 marks a microglial state in AD: in apolipoprotein E knockout mice, overexpression of triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 promoted polarization towards an Arg1⁺ phenotype, reduced pro-inflammatory signalling, and increased brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) production and hippocampal neurogenesis, supporting a neuroprotective role for Arg1⁺ microglia [141].

Astrocytes also undergo arginase-related remodelling. A β oligomer exposure induce astrocytic Arg1 along with CPS1, OTC and ASL (Figure 1), effectively reconstituting physiologically incomplete brain urea cycle to detoxify excessive ammonia generated during A β degradation [6]. This shift is mirrored in human AD hippocampus, where upregulation of urea cycle enzymes associate with elevated Put and GABA, linking arginase induction to neuromodulation [6]. Neuronal models provide additional, although divergent insights. In mutant APP-overexpressing neuron-like PC12 cells, Arg1, Arg2 and ASS are reduced, while ASL is selectively upregulated [142,143].

Collectively, these data indicate that arginase dysregulation is a prominent and multifaceted feature of AD. Multiple lines of evidence indicate altered arginase expression and activity in AD brain, implicating dysregulated Arg→Orn metabolism in pathogenesis. A substantial number of studies support increased Arg1 and/or Arg2 in affected regions, particularly hippocampus and SFG, despite some transcriptomic discrepancies reflecting cell-type and stage specificity. Experimental models reveal spatially distinct regulation, with early Arg1 induction in glia linked to immune modulation and neuroprotection, and Arg2 localized mainly to neurons. Astrocytes additionally show arginase-dependent reprogramming,

including partial urea cycle activation in attempt to manage ammonia generated during A β pathology, but with pathological consequences.

PD. Compared with AD, arginase is less studied in PD patients. In *post-mortem* brains from patients with multiple system atrophy (MSA), a disorder related to PD through shared α -synuclein (α Syn) pathology, Arg1 mRNA was significantly decreased in the frontal lobe, together with upregulation of pro-inflammatory factors, suggesting microglial/macrophage polarization towards an M1 phenotype [144]. Similar observations – loss of Arg1 expression or Arg1-positive microglia accompanied by increased pro-inflammatory microglia, were reported in the SNpc across multiple *in vivo* PD models, including MPTP-exposed mice [145–148], 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA)-exposed mice [149], lipopolysaccharide-exposed mice [150], rotenone-exposed rats [151] and A53T mutant α Syn-expressing mice [152]. A similar age-dependent decline in Arg1 was also observed in SNpc of wild-type, untreated rats [153]. Interestingly, recent single-cell RNA sequencing study identified Arg1, together with several inflammatory genes, as a marker of a novel pro-inflammatory microglial subpopulation in α Syn transgenic mouse model of the cerebellar variant of MSA, in which these cells surrounded α Syn aggregates and their abundance correlated with the extent of neuropathology and motor decline [154]. This finding may suggest that Arg1 expression in microglia in synucleinopathies doesn't invariably indicate an anti-inflammatory phenotype, although further research is needed to define the functional significance of this microglial population.

Although Arg2 is especially enriched in the striatum [28,55], a region that receives dense DA input from the SNpc and is critically involved in PD pathogenesis and motor circuitry impairment, disease-related alterations of this isoenzyme have not been studied. A single *in vitro* report shows that pharmacologically induced Arg2 overexpression protects both PC12 cells and primary midbrain neurons from 6-OHDA neurotoxicity. The proposed mechanism involves competition between Arg2 and NOS for Arg, so that Arg2 upregulation reduces 6-OHDA-induced NO generation, thus limiting mitochondrial damage and cell death [155].

Thus, unlike AD, arginase is understudied in PD. Available data from model studies, however, consistently demonstrate that PD and related synucleinopathies are associated with loss of Arg1-positive anti-inflammatory microglia, often linked to pro-inflammatory activation. The role of Arg2 in PD remains largely unexplored despite limited *in vitro* evidence for neuroprotective effects.

HD. Direct analyses of arginase in *post-mortem* human HD brain are limited, but the anatomical context is informative. The striatum is the earliest and most affected structure in HD, with selective vulnerability of MSNs [156]. Notably, Arg2 is an MSN-specific protein in the striatum, absent from glia [28], suggesting that any perturbations in this protein can directly impact the degenerating neuronal population.

Unlike AD, there is no consistent evidence for robust arginase disturbances in HD patients brain. Conversely, experimental models support progressive impairment of arginase. In YAC128Q mice, striatal arginase activity is significantly reduced at the presymptomatic stage despite preserved Arg2, followed by marked Arg2 protein deficiency with disease progression [55], which was confirmed in another HD model, R6/2 mice [55]. These findings are reinforced by available genomics/proteomics data, showing CAG length-dependent loss of striatal Arg2 protein in HD knock-in mice. Interestingly, Arg2 protein alterations in these

models are not accompanied by mRNA changes, suggesting post-transcriptional regulation of Arg2 in HD.[55,157].

Although the pathogenic significance of Arg2 remains unclear in HD, its loss causes pronounced polyamine dyshomeostasis [25], and is associated with a distinct metabolic signature enriched for NADH pathway alterations and mitochondrial dysfunction in Arg2 knockout (KO) striatum [28]. Together, these findings link Arg2 deficit in the striatum to broader mitochondrial and redox disturbances, processes already implicated in HD pathogenesis.

Arginase dysregulation in HD models also extends beyond the CNS. HTT pathology is present in the liver and hepatic dysfunction occur in HD models [158]. In R6/2 mice, hepatic expression and activity of urea cycle enzymes, including ASS, ASL, and Arg1, are reduced contributing to disturbances in Arg/urea metabolism [159,160]. Arginase activity loss also appears to be reflected by changes in Arg/Orn ratio in the blood of the aforementioned presymptomatic HD sheep [120]. Conversely, in neuronal line expressing pathological protein with 57 Gln repeats (Q57 line), a model of polyglutamine (polyQ) diseases, Arg1 is increased and contributes to aggregation and cell injury [161].

Overall, although HD patient data are scarce, model studies suggest a progressive loss of striatal Arg2 and peripheral Arg1, consistent with metabolic changes observed over the course of the disease. Increased Arg1 in polyQ neurons highlights pronounced isoenzyme-, tissue-, and cell type-specific regulation.

ALS. As in HD, data on arginase in ALS patients are limited. One study reported significantly increased catalytic activity in the CSF of ALS patients compared with controls [162]. Most insight therefore comes from experimental models. In the healthy mouse lumbar spinal cord, Arg1 is expressed in motor neurons and increases with age, while in SOD1^{G93A} mice, Arg1 immunoreactivity, protein levels, and enzymatic activity decline with disease progression [138], however, according to another report its loss is lower than that of Arg1-negative neurons [163]. Consistently, Arg1 mRNA is reduced at both, symptom onset and the end-stage, in spinal regions (but not cortex) in this model and SOD1^{G93A} rats [164–166], although in these reports Arg1 loss is attributed to microglia and associated with a shift towards a proinflammatory M1 phenotype. Reduced Arg1 is also observed in lumbar spinal cord of mice overexpressing syncytin-1, an ALS-associated gene [167], indicating cross-model consistency. Microglial involvement in Arg1 loss is demonstrated in an *in vitro* study, in which exposure of primary rat microglia to ALS patient-derived CSF induces Arg1 loss together with increased iNOS, resulting in an elevated iNOS/Arg1 ratio and polarization towards a pro-inflammatory microglial phenotype [168]. In contrast, dogs with degenerative myelopathy, a naturally occurring disease considered a close analogue of human ALS, show increased Arg1-positive microglia near lumbar motor neurons [169]. Nevertheless, across these studies, Arg2 involvement has not been reported, indicating that ALS-associated arginase alterations predominantly involve Arg1 in spinal immune and neuronal compartments.

In summary, AD shows robust arginase dysregulation, with increased Arg1 and/or Arg2 linking altered arginase activity to neuronal and glial dysfunction. In PD, available data indicate loss or reprogramming of Arg1-positive microglia toward pro-inflammatory states, while Arg2 remains largely unexplored. HD is characterized by early, MSNs-specific loss of striatal Arg2, with additional peripheral Arg1 deficits contributing to metabolic vulnerability.

Finally, ALS displays Arg1 loss associated with microglial polarization towards M1 phenotype, although Arg1-expressing spinal motor neurons appear to be relatively protected from degeneration compared with other neuronal subpopulations. Arginase dysregulation, therefore, emerges as a common, yet disease-specific mechanism across neurodegeneration, linking Arg handling to inflammation, metabolism and neuronal vulnerability.

Arginase as a contributor to neurodegeneration

Arginase remodelling (Arg1/Arg2 induction, redistribution, or loss) alters Arg allocation between protein synthesis, and competing metabolic routes, which are tightly linked with crucial cellular processes including redox balance, mitochondrial function, neurotransmission and neuromodulation, immune signalling, ammonia detoxification or cell death/survival pathways among others. Consequently, even moderate arginase changes can propagate into broader neurodegenerative or neuroprotective cascades. Arginase can therefore be either detrimental or beneficial in the course of neurodegeneration, highlighting strong isoenzyme-, cell type-, and disease stage-dependence.

Ammonia and urea metabolism. Arginase-catalysed Arg→Orn conversion generates urea as a by-product. Since ureagenesis is normally low in brain, increased arginase flux or induction of additional urea cycle components leads to urea overproduction, necessitating enhanced urea handling or clearance. Dysregulated urea cycling/trafficking is increasingly implicated in AD, PD and HD [44,69,123,170].

In Aβ-conditioned reactive astrocytes, urea cycle upregulation is accompanied by increased expression of UT-B [6]. Similarly, UT-B is upregulated in the striatum of prodromal HD sheep, coinciding with elevated tissue urea levels [122]. Although this response may initially facilitate ammonia detoxification, generated during enhanced protein degradation, it can also activate aberrant astrocytic Orn→Put→GABA pathway, as shown in Aβ-exposed astrocytes [171]. Consequently, arginase-driven diversion of nitrogen towards Orn and urea may contribute directly to disease phenotypes.

On the other hand, evidence from HD models indicates that peripheral urea cycle insufficiency, including reduced hepatic Arg1, elevates circulating ammonia [159,160]. Ammonia is a highly neurotoxic metabolite and its impaired hepatic detoxification is particularly detrimental to the brain [172]. In hepatic Arg1-deficient R6/2 mice, hyperammonaemia contributes significantly to motor impairment, striatal HTT aggregation and BDNF reduction [123].

Overall, overactivation of arginase-driven flux of Arg towards Orn in the neurodegenerative brain predisposes to urea accumulation and engages aberrant metabolic pathways that promote overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and ammonia, while hepatic Arg1 loss elevates blood ammonia levels, supporting a model in which arginase and urea-cycle dysregulation actively contribute to disease phenotypes.

Competition with NOS. NOS and arginase compete for Arg; shifting Arg towards arginase can reduce physiological NO production, whereas shifting it towards NOS can increase NO/radical nitrogen species (RNS). Both directions can be harmful or protective depending on tissue, isoform, cell type and disease stage.

eNOS-derived NO stabilizes the vascular microenvironment and supports vasodilation and blood supply, reducing neuronal susceptibility to oxidative stress [173–175] whereas NO produced by nNOS regulates synaptic plasticity and cognition [176–178]. Reduced NO bioavailability contributes to cerebrovascular dysfunction [179], a condition implicated in pathogenesis of different forms of dementia [180]. Dysregulated synaptic NO signalling has also been proposed as a contributor to multiple neurodegenerative pathologies [181]. Consistently, NO donors protect against A β toxicity in neuronal AD models [182,183], whereas high-salt diet promotes tau phosphorylation and memory impairment via loss of eNOS activity [184]. In addition, the second NOS product, Cit, has been shown to exert neuroprotective effects and improve memory in brain ischemia model [185]. Together, these findings suggest that NO depletion via arginase upregulation may be detrimental in contexts, where NOS is required for vascular and synaptic support.

Conversely, shifting Arg towards NOS can induce NO overproduction, that, particularly via iNOS-expressing pro-inflammatory neuroglia, drives neurotoxicity [186,187]. A β -triggered NO promotes mitochondrial fission and synaptic loss [188]. In PD, abundant iNOS-positive microglia accumulate in SNpc and other DA midbrain regions [189,190], and blocking nNOS or iNOS protects against DA degeneration in toxin models [191–195]. In ALS, iNOS-positive cells increase in patient and mouse spinal cord early in disease [125,163,196,197], with microglial NO/peroxynitrite significantly contributing to early disease development [198].

In PD as well as in AD and other tauopathies, nitrosative stress is widespread and frequently targets disease-specific aggregating proteins, contributing to different stages of their aggregation [199–203]. Meanwhile, Arg1 overexpression in the rTg4510 tau mouse model reduces tau deposition; the authors propose that arginase-mediated competition for Arg limits NO toxicity, resulting in decreased tau nitration at aggregation-promoting Tyr18 site and reduced iNOS-dependent neuroinflammation [204]. In this context, Arg1 effectively channels Arg away from NO/RNS production, protecting cells from tauopathy and its consequences.

Overall, arginase–NOS competition is a regulatory mechanism whose ultimate effect depends on NOS isoform, cellular compartment and disease stage, rather than being intrinsically beneficial or harmful.

Polyamine pathway dysregulation. Polyamine homeostasis follows a biphasic relationship: both excess and depletion are harmful. ODC overexpression and polyamine excess impair spatial learning [205], whereas difluoromethylornithine (DFMO)-induced Put depletion disrupts recognition memory [206], indicating a narrow physiological window. In AD, strong dysregulation of polyamine genes has been reported. In PS19 mice, chronic elevated expression of antizyme inhibitor 2 (AZIN2), a polyamine synthesis disinhibiting factor, induced a maladaptive polyamine stress response with accumulation of acetylpolyamines accompanied by enhanced tau pathology and worsened cognition [207]. Mechanistically, higher-order polyamines (Spd/Spm) displace tau from microtubules, facilitating polymerization, while acetylpolyamines promote tau oligomerization and seeding [207]. Excessive polyamine synthesis and recycling may additionally promote pathological tau phosphorylation [208]. In the CVN-AD model, inhibition of the arginase/polyamine pathway with DFMO reduced Arg loss observed in this model, decreased A β deposition and improved memory [89].

Conversely, polyamines are well-established autophagy inducers [209,210]. Spd, via autophagy activation, reduces soluble neurotoxic A β and microglial activation in APP/PS1

mice [211], enhances spatial learning in aged mice and aversive olfactory memory in *D. melanogaster* aging model [212] as well as protects against memory impairment in an AD *C. elegans* model [213]. Similarly, Spm promotes autophagy-mediated aggregate degradation, contributing to improved motor performance and lifespan in α Syn-expressing *C. elegans* [214].

In PD, similar effects are observed. Polyamines promote α Syn aggregate assembly in a charge-dependent manner (Spm>Spd>Put) [215,216], with Spd accelerating early misfolding and dimer formation [217]. On the other hand, polyamines can be protective by inducing autophagy [218,219] and mitophagy [213] in PD models, highlighting dose- and compartment-specific effects. A direct link between polyamine homeostasis and PD has been established via ATP13A2/PARK9, an endolysosomal protein mutated in Kufor–Rakeb syndrome, an early-onset PD with dementia [220]. ATP13A2 was recently identified as a polyamine transporter that mediates lysosome-to-cytosol polyamine transport, while disease-related mutations disrupt this process, leading to lysosomal polyamine accumulation, cytosolic polyamine deficiency and PD-like neurodegeneration, whereas wild-type ATP13A2 rescues PD-like phenotypes [221–223].

In HD-like model, ODC activation increased aggregation and death in Q57 HTT cells, consistent with a self-reinforcing mechanism, where Spm binding to polyQ depletes free Spm and drives compensatory synthesis that further fuels aggregation [161]. In contrast, *in vivo*, Spm protected against gliosis in quinolinic acid HD rat model [224].

Collectively, these findings place polyamines as a key determinant of neuronal dyshomeostasis in neurodegeneration. By controlling polyamine homeostasis, both, Arg1 and Arg2 may regulate critical processes related with pathology including autophagy and aggregation.

Inflammation and immune regulation. Arg1 is a hallmark of alternative immune activation and suppresses inflammatory responses by depleting Arg, thereby shaping innate immune functions. This can be neuroprotective by limiting inflammation or maladaptive, when chronic immune suppression impairs clearance of pathological proteins. In AD models, a CD11c⁺ microglial population co-accumulating with extracellular Arg1 and A β , and expressing immunosuppressive markers, was shown to be reduced by DFMO in parallel with improved pathology and behaviour [89], supporting a role for microglial Arg1 in maintaining local suppression while remodelling Arg availability. A β can also directly perturb microglial Arg metabolism by disrupting the balance between ODC and its endogenous inhibitor, antizyme, driving a pro-inflammatory M1 phenotype, while restoring ODC suppressed inflammatory markers and reduced microglial cytotoxicity [225]. These findings indicate that regulation of Arg→Orn→polyamine branch actively shapes microglial polarization in neurodegenerative settings. Consistently, in a rapidly progressive MSA-C model, single-cell RNAseq identified a pro-inflammatory microglial subset with high Arg1 expression near phosphorylated α Syn aggregates, implicated in aggressive pathology [154], highlighting that Arg1 marks context-dependent microglial states, that in some settings can be pathogenic rather than uniformly protective.

Mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress. Impairment of bioenergetic metabolism is a key contributor to neurodegeneration [226,227], with alterations in mitochondrial bioenergetics preceding disease phenotypes in the model systems [228–230]. Mitochondrial

arginase isoenzyme, Arg2, is directly linked to mitochondrial function as its loss reduces mitochondrial membrane potential and oxygen consumption rate [231]. Therefore, neuronal Arg2 dysfunction may impair oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), sensitizing neurons to aggregated proteins, excitotoxicity, and inflammatory signals. The possible mechanism may involve polyamines, which are known to affect mitochondrial performance through multiple pathways. Polyamine-mediated hypusination of eukaryotic initiation factor 5A (eIF5A) stimulates OXPHOS proteins synthesis across tissues [232,233], including brain, where Spd, by increasing eIF5A hypusination, improved mitochondrial function from age-related decline in *D. melanogaster* [234] and mice [212]. Spd and Spm also protect neuronal mitochondria and bioenergetic metabolism via autophagy-mediated maintenance of mitochondrial proteins, improving cognitive decline in senescence accelerated mouse-8 aging model [235]. In cellular tauopathy models, Spd restores mitochondrial respiration, membrane potential, and ATP production, while correcting tau-induced mitophagy defects [236].

On the other hand, polyamines regulate mitochondrial calcium uniporter (MCU), with Spm acting as a potent MCU opener [237]. MCU-mediated Ca_2^+ uptake enhances mitochondrial respiration [238], but during pathology, such as excitotoxicity, with sustained cytosolic $[\text{Ca}_2^+]$ elevation, leads to mitochondria Ca_2^+ overload, mitochondrial membrane depolarization and activation of cell death pathways [239]. MCU involvement in neurodegeneration has been demonstrated in multiple models [240–243], positioning polyamines as a potential contributor to cell death via MCU regulation. However, a biphasic effect of polyamines on MCU has recently been described, where at high cytosolic $[\text{Ca}_2^+]$, polyamines, particularly Spm, inhibit mitochondrial Ca_2^+ entry [244], potentially providing protection. Overall, these findings position polyamines as a metabolic regulator coupling Arg flux to mitochondrial function through multiple mechanisms, with mitochondrial Arg2 localization suggesting a role in polyamine synthesis regulation in response to mitochondrial demands.

Mitochondrial dysfunction promotes oxidative stress, a major contributor to neurodegeneration. An additional arginase-related ROS source is oxidative polyamine degradation, which generates reactive byproducts such as acrolein, implicated in ischemic stroke, PD, and MS [245–247]. Acrolein induces severe oxidative stress, and, in AD models drives amyloidogenic processing, hippocampal atrophy and cognitive decline [78,248,249], while in PD models it promotes αSyn aggregation and DA neuron loss [250,251]. $\text{A}\beta$ -induced activation of astrocytic Arg1 and the urea cycle increases Put oxidative degradation accompanied by ROS accumulation, whereas Arg1 silencing protects against redox imbalance and cognitive deficits in APP/PS1 AD mice [6], implicating arginase in polyamine-driven oxidative stress and resulting pathology.

Neurotransmission and neuromodulation. The position of arginase at the intersection of neuroactive metabolite pathways makes it a regulator of neurotransmitter and neuromodulator synthesis. Among these, polyamines are well-established modulators of glutamatergic neurotransmission, with Spd and, especially, Spm potentiating N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDAR) [249]. In rat retina, excessive NMDAR activation increases Arg1 expression in glia, enhancing polyamine-mediated NMDAR potentiation and retinal ganglion cell death, while DFMO is protective in this model [252]. Similarly, in the brain, blocking the NMDAR polyamine site or inhibiting polyamine synthesis reverses memory impairment in $\text{A}\beta$ -exposed mice [253], implicating arginase-mediated Orn delivery in pathological NMDAR potentiation. NO further intersects with excitotoxicity, as chronic NMDAR-NO-cGMP pathway overactivation drives motor neuron-selective death in ALS [254], and microglial NO/peroxynitrite potentiates glutamate toxicity [198]. Finally, Agm, produced from Arg via a

pathway concurrent with arginase, also acts as a versatile neuromodulator, that inhibits NMDAR [255,256]. Thus, by supporting polyamine production and competing with Arg and NO synthesis, arginase controls the balance between NMDAR activation and inhibition, contributing to NMDAR-mediated neuronal injury.

The polyamine pathway can also generate GABA: in APP/PS1 mice hippocampus, increased expression of Arg1 and ODC in reactive astrocytes supports MAO-B-mediated conversion of Put to GABA, which, upon release, contributes to memory impairment [6,257].

Figure 2 provides a schematic overview of the major cellular pathways through which arginase may contribute to neurodegeneration.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the major cellular pathways linking arginase and its downstream metabolic pathways to mechanisms involved in neurodegeneration. Mechanisms shown in red are induced by a decrease in the levels/activity of indicated arginase

isoforms/metabolites, mechanisms shown in purple are induced by an increase in the levels/activity of indicated arginase isoforms/metabolites. Abbreviations: Arg – arginine, Arg1 – arginase 1, Arg2 – arginase 2, CBF – cerebral blood flow, GABA - γ -aminobutyric acid, NO – nitric oxide, Orn – ornithine.

Therapeutic perspectives

A proper understanding of alterations in Arg metabolism in neurodegeneration will guide intervention strategies targeting arginase and its downstream pathways to normalize Arg fate (among arginase, NOS, AGAT and ADC), and buffer downstream effects (ammonia/urea load, redox stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, neurotransmitter imbalance, immune polarization). However, isoenzyme-, cell type-, brain region-, and disease stage-specific targeting remains a central design principle.

Dietary Arg supplementation. Evidence support potential benefits of dietary Arg in dementia and ALS. In senile dementia patients, daily Arg supplementation (1.6 g/day, 3 months) improved cognitive function [258]. In experimental models, chronic intracerebroventricular Arg delivery improved spatial memory in 3xTg-AD mice [259], while oral Arg suppressed A β aggregation and reduced plaque accumulation in *D. melanogaster* and mouse AD models, with improved spatial memory in mice [260]. Similarly, intraperitoneal Arg injections reduced hippocampal and cortical A β accumulation and protected from spatial learning deficit in a rat model of diabetes-associated AD [261].

In ALS, Arg demonstrates promising effects in preclinical and early clinical studies. Dietary Arg protected SOD1^{G93A} mice from polyamine loss, increased Arg1 levels, reduced motor neuron loss and muscle wasting and delayed motor impairment and death [138]. In patients, an open-label trial of oral Arg HCl (15 g/day for 90 days) showed good tolerability without serious adverse effects [262], supporting feasibility for future studies .

Together, these data suggest that Arg supplementation may be beneficial, particularly in settings, where Arg is limiting for protective pathways, but potentially risky when diverted into toxic pathways (such as excessive NOS-driven stress or maladaptive urea/polyamine flux), underscoring the need for biomarker-guided selection and precise stage-, tissue- or cell-targeted delivery.

Polyamine pathway modulation. Because arginase remodeling can shift flux into Orn and polyamines, polyamines themselves emerge as therapeutic candidates. Maintaining adequate polyamine pools can support autophagy and OXPHOS, while excess polyamines generate toxic byproducts, support NMDAR overactivation and promote protein aggregation. Accordingly, interventions targeting this pathway in different model systems show mixed outcomes, with benefits reported for both polyamine support and inhibition.

As mentioned before, polyamine supplementation has beneficial effects across multiple neurodegenerative models, mediated by restoration of mitochondrial function [212,235,236] and/or autophagy activation [211,212,214]. Other trials confirmed beneficial effect of polyamines, particularly Spd, in different settings. Spd protected SNpc DA neurons and improved motor performance in a rotenone rat PD model [263], reduced oxidative stress,

neuroinflammation and motor deficits in a 3-nitropropionic acid (3-NPA) rat HD model [264], and preserved spinal neurons, reduced gliosis and rescued motor deficits in SOD1^{G93A} ALS mouse model [265]. In TAR DNA-binding protein 43 (TDP-43)-expressing mice, Spd improved motor outcomes in association with increased autophagy markers [266]. Finally, in humans higher dietary Spd intake was associated with lower risk of cognitive impairment and improved memory and executive function with a dose–response relationship. These associations were robust across multiple demographic and dietary adjustments, suggesting Spd as an independent dietary factor linked to preserved cognitive function [212].

A key translational concern is safety and tolerability, given the established involvement of excessive polyamines and ODC overexpression in tumour biology [267–269], underscoring the need for careful dosing and monitoring. Addressing this, a double-blind, placebo-controlled phase II trial showed that three months of Spd-enriched wheat germ extract was well tolerated in older adults with cognitive decline, with no tumorigenic or fibrotic signals [263]. While efficacy remains to be proven in larger trials, these data help justify longer-term studies.

Another long-standing issue concerns BBB penetration. Polyamines, in contrast to Arg, are generally thought to cross BBB poorly under physiological conditions [38], yet Put and Spd can transiently disrupt BBB integrity when injected intracarotidly [270]. In addition, BBB disruption during ischemia permits nonspecific brain entry of exogenous polyamines [271], while later study demonstrated both nonspecific and later specific Spd transport into multiple regions, particularly hippocampus [272]. Given that BBB disruption is common in neurodegeneration and aging [273] polyamine brain penetration may be enhanced in such conditions. Consistently, Spd administration in drinking water increased brain Spd levels in aged mice [212], supporting potential therapeutic strategies based on polyamine supplementation.

Conversely, excessive polyamine accumulation can also drive pathology, and inhibition strategies have also been explored. As mentioned before, DFMO improved pathology in CVN-AD mice [89], although a compassionate, single-case DFMO trial in MCI patient failed to halt cognitive decline or A β accumulation, with progression to AD type dementia despite 12 months of treatment [274]. As most polyamine-lowering preclinical studies use DFMO to target the pathway at its first step, there remains room for alternative approaches to selectively inhibit higher polyamines, using SMR inhibitors, such as decarboxylated S-adenosylhomocysteine [275], trans-4-methylcyclohexylamine [276] or 2-Mercaptoethylamine [277], or SMS inhibitors, such as N-(3-aminopropyl)cyclohexylamine [277] or S-methyl-5'-methylthioadenosine (MMTA) [278].

Finally, considering the contribution of the oxidative Put→GABA pathway in reactive astrocytes to the pathology [6], MAO-B inhibition appears to be an attractive strategy, as it would simultaneously target neurotransmitter imbalance and nitrogen/oxidative stress amplification. Irreversible MAO-B inhibitors (rasagiline, L-deprenyl) showed neuroprotective effects in AD patients [279], while the reversible inhibitor, KDS2010, maintained GABA levels and improved learning and memory in APP/PS1 mice more effectively than L-deprenyl [280].

Overall, considering the beneficial effects of Spd and detrimental effects of Spm and Put→GABA pathway, a combined strategy of Spd supplementation with MAO-B and SMS inhibition may be most promising, though it would require careful optimization and testing.

Agm supplementation. Agm exerts beneficial brain effects through multiple pathways and has been tested in a number of preclinical studies in neurodegeneration. Agm induces antizyme and downregulates Put production [281]. In A β -exposed mice, intra-hippocampal Agm improved learning and memory [282], while intracerebroventricular Agm reduced depressive-like behaviour [283], in both cases reducing neuroinflammation, consistent with iNOS inhibition by Agm [284]. In a rotenone rat PD model, intraperitoneal Agm reduced oxidative damage, neuronal loss and motor deficits [285], while in a 3-NPA HD model, it normalized striatal neurochemical dyshomeostasis, reduced MSNs loss and improved motor coordination [286]. Agm-mediated NMDAR inhibition contributed to SNpc DA neuron protection and motor improvement in rotenone-exposed rats [287], as well as protection against dyskinesia and DA content loss in reserpine-treated mice [288] and memory loss in streptozotocin AD rat model [289]. Importantly, long-term high-dose Agm intake in humans (2.67 g/day for 4–5 years) showed no adverse effects, supporting its safety and encouraging testing in neurodegenerative diseases [290].

Arginase inhibition. Direct modulation of arginase appears to be attractive because it controls Arg allocation. In 3xTg-AD mice, 10 weeks of treatment with the arginase inhibitor, L-norvaline provided in drinking water, resulted in increased synaptic protein expression, higher spine density, decreased APP and reduced amyloid plaque load in hippocampus and prefrontal cortex accompanied by reduced microgliosis, more resting microglial state and significantly improved memory acquisition [50,291]. Considering maladaptive urea cycle activation in AD astrocytes, including overexpression of Arg1, arginase inhibition may also ameliorate consequences of altered astrocytic Arg metabolism, such as enhanced GABA neurotransmission, and ROS and ammonia accumulation. Notably, ammonia levels were shown to be reduced following Arg1 gene silencing in A β -treated astrocytes via decreased MAO-B-mediated degradation of Arg1- and ODC1-derived Put [6], additionally supporting rationale for arginase inhibition in AD.

However, indiscriminate arginase blocking carries a significant risks. Arg1 is essential for the hepatic urea cycle, and its deficiency causes severe urea cycle disorders, making systemic arginase inhibition susceptible to hyperammonemia [292]. Accordingly, therapeutic strategies should prioritize cell- or region-targeted approaches and, where possible, isoenzyme selectivity. Additionally, given that metabolic remodelling begins early in neurodegeneration, arginase inhibition would likely be most effective at preclinical stages, which would require the development of AD-specific early biomarker panels to enable screening studies and ensure sufficiently early treatment initiation, consistent with the limited efficacy of middle-stage DFMO intervention [89].

Ammonia detoxification strategies. Ammonia and urea dysregulation occurs across multiple neurodegenerative disorders [93,110,122], supporting therapeutic strategies that reduce ammonia load or enhance safe disposal. In AD-reactive astrocytes, silencing of ARG1, ODC and MAO-B each attenuated toxic ammonia levels and suppressed maladaptive urea cycle program *in vitro* [6], indicating that targeting multiple nodes of the nitrogen disposal pathway can limit ammonia amplification.

Beyond enzyme inhibitors, metabolic approaches may include protein-restricted diet, as shown to improve metabolic outcomes [293] and cognition in AD model [294]. Additionally, as ammonia scavengers are already used in hepatic encephalopathy [295], repurposing them for neurodegeneration with ammonia/urea signatures is plausible route, but likely requires careful patient stratification. Another complementary strategy is supporting physiological

ammonia detoxification, particularly via glutamine synthetase (GS), a major cerebral ammonia clearance pathway [296]. This strategy may be particularly relevant, given astrocytic localization of GS [297] and the fact that astrocytes are a major source of excess endogenous ammonia in AD brain [6], and possibly other neurodegenerative disorders.

NO modulation. Therapeutic modulation of NO may depend on whether the dominant pathology is primarily driven by excessive toxic or insufficient protective NO. Numerous studies report beneficial effects of general NOS inhibition or targeted inhibition/silencing of specific NOS isoforms, including reduced neuroinflammation, RNS accumulation and protein aggregation, improved behavioural outcomes and prolonged survival in preclinical models of AD/dementia [298,299], PD [300,301] and ALS [302]. On the other hand, reduced NO may result in neurovascular dysfunction, and impairment in cerebral blood flow (CBF) significantly contributes to the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative diseases, especially dementia. Accordingly, in AD, strategies enhancing eNOS function may be beneficial, as shown by combined treatment with simvastatin (3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A inhibitor, increasing eNOS activity), Arg (as eNOS substrate) and tetrahydrobiopterin (THB; NOS cofactor) which increased CBF and produced modest cognitive improvements in patients with MCI and mild AD [303]

An additional strategy to regulate NO synthesis may involve modulation of arginase to control Arg availability for NOS. Although the arginase K_m for Arg (~2 mM) is nearly 1000-fold higher than the NOS K_m for Arg (~3 μ M for eNOS), the V_{max} of NOS is approximately 1000-fold lower than that of arginase [304,305], making these two enzymes direct competitors for Arg. Numerous studies have demonstrated competition between arginase and NOS for Arg, and this competition has been proposed to contribute to the so called arginine paradox, the observation that supplementation of cells with Arg increases NO production, even though intracellular Arg concentrations are already well above the NOS K_m and should, in theory, saturate the enzyme [306]. In addition to the direct competition between NOS and arginase for Arg, also metabolites produced in arginase-related pathways have been shown to inhibit NOS. iNOS is inhibited by urea [307,308], and both iNOS [309] and nNOS [310] are inhibited by polyamines, with Spm being the most potent. Finally, Arg2 regulates the distribution of Ca^{2+} between mitochondria and cytosol, reducing cytosolic Ca^{2+} availability for calmodulin, what was reported to inhibit eNOS, a calmodulin-dependent enzyme [311]. Overall, arginase emerges as a critical regulator of cellular NO synthesis in the cell and potential therapeutic target in NOS-aimed strategies in neurodegeneration, which, depending on disease context, could involve arginase activation or inhibition, alone or in combination with NOS modulators, to achieve more precise control of NO production.

Developing arginase PET radiotracers. Positron emission tomography (PET) tracers targeting arginase have been proposed as an approach to map structures of altered arginase expression in patients. Although no arginase-specific PET tracers are currently available, the authors propose repurposing existing arginase inhibitors, particularly boronic acid-based compounds such as S-(2-boronoethyl)-L-cysteine (BEC), 2-amino-6-borono-2-methylhexanoic acid (MABH) or 2-Amino-6-borono-2-(difluoromethyl)hexanoic acid (FABH). These inhibitors display high yet reversible binding affinity to arginase and rapid systemic clearance, properties that are well suited for PET imaging and may improve target-to-background signal [3].

In the context of neurodegeneration, an arginase PET ligand could provide spatial insight into disease-associated metabolic reprogramming, microglia polarization and the injury or loss of

specific neuronal populations. Potential applications include imaging astrocytic Arg1 in AD, where Arg1 is associated with maladaptive activation of the urea cycle and contributes to pathology; monitoring microglial Arg1 expression to assess polarization towards an M2 phenotype in different diseases and detecting Arg1 in spinal motor neurons to track neurodegeneration in ALS. Imaging Arg2 in striatal MSNs may also be of interest for monitoring neurodegeneration in HD, although this approach may be challenging due to the intramitochondrial localization of Arg2, which limits accessibility to PET radioligands.

Overall, arginase PET imaging could be valuable for identifying disease heterogeneity and for monitoring pharmacological approaches in trials and therapies. Its non-invasive nature would enable longitudinal assessment of arginase expression over the course of disease progression or in response to therapy.

In summary, arginase represents a promising therapeutic target: an enzyme whose modulation can redirect metabolic, signalling and stress-related pathways. The most likely successful approaches will likely be precision strategies, supported by biomarkers and delivered to the relevant cell type/region, and optimized for disease stage, rather than uniform inhibition or activation across the CNS and periphery. Therapeutic perspectives relevant to arginase and its associated pathways in neurodegeneration are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Therapeutic perspectives targeting arginase-related metabolic pathways and their consequences in neurodegeneration. Enzymatic modulation, metabolic supplementation, ammonia detoxification strategies, dietary interventions, and imaging approaches are proposed.

Future directions of arginase research

Our understanding of arginase in CNS physiology and pathology still contains substantial gaps. To advance current knowledge, several future directions and open questions need to be addressed.

Cell-type specific functions of Arg1 vs Arg2. Future studies should aim to characterize the roles of arginase isoenzymes across distinct CNS cell types. Conditional knockout models, for example, Arg1 deletion selective for microglia or Arg2 deletion restricted to selected neuronal subpopulations, will help to clarify how each isoenzyme contributes to disease phenotypes. Single-cell transcriptomics of patient brains tissue could further complement these studies by revealing which cell populations up- or down-regulate Arg1 or Arg2 as disease progresses. Together, such studies will help determine whether therapeutic strategies should target both isoenzymes or rather one selectively. This should be accompanied by the development of isoenzyme-specific approaches. At present, none of the available arginase inhibitors exhibits pronounced specificity to Arg1 or Arg2, and such selectivity would be required for more precise therapeutic interventions.

Longitudinal studies in patients. Cross-sectional studies reveal differences in Arg1/Arg2 and related metabolites in patients, however, longitudinal data are required to understand how they change as neurodegeneration progresses or in response to therapy. For example, do Arg1/Arg2 expression or activity and downstream metabolite profiles change when AD patients convert from MCI to dementia or when carriers of mutant Htt are diagnosed with HD? Multi-omics techniques could be applied in clinical studies to address these questions. Such studies may establish arginase-related metabolic signatures as early biomarkers or progression indicators.

Arginase in less studied disorders. While AD, PD, HD, and ALS are primary focus, Arg metabolism may also play important roles in other neurodegenerative conditions. Other tauopathies, like FTD, Pick's disease or PSP; synucleinopathies, including MSA and dementia with Lewy bodies; or polyQ disorders such as spinocerebellar ataxias or spinal and bulbar muscular atrophy require thorough investigation in the context of arginase and related metabolism. Such studies would help determine whether shared patterns exist across neurodegeneration in general, within specific disease groups, or across particular cell types or affected regions. Expanding research into these areas will determine whether potential therapeutic strategies targeting arginase could have broader neuroprotective applications in neurodegeneration.

Mitochondrial Arg2 mechanisms. Arg2 is less well studied than Arg1, and both, its precise distribution in the brain and its cellular functions remain poorly characterized. In particular, the mechanistic relationship between Arg2 and mitochondrial functioning remains to be properly elucidated. Key open questions include: how important Arg2-derived Orn is for mitochondrial metabolism - is it predominantly processed in mitochondria by OAT or exported and utilized by ODC; why Arg2 expression is restricted to selected neuronal subpopulations (for example MSNs) and what is its role in these specific cells; and whether Arg2 has some non-canonical functions, independent of Arg metabolism. Addressing these questions would require single-cell or spatial omics approaches, targeted genetic manipulation in animal models, high-resolution imaging of mitochondria in neurons with Arg2 deletion or overexpression, and identification of Arg2-interacting cellular partners. Moreover, given that Arg2 generates urea within mitochondria, it will be important to

investigate how urea is exported from this compartment and whether intramitochondrial urea accumulation affects mitochondrial function.

Integration with multi-omics. Future research should integrate metabolomic data with genomic and proteomic approaches to achieve a comprehensive view of arginase regulation. For example, if individuals carrying specific Arg2 polymorphism (such as rs742869) that are associated with disease risk, exhibit distinct disease course or differential responses to therapy. Combining genomic data with metabolite profiles and imaging measures could help to identify molecularly defined patient subgroups. In addition, analysis of disease-associated post-translational modifications of arginase isoenzymes could provide insight into regulatory mechanisms and uncover new therapeutic targets.

Conclusion

Arginase serves as a critical regulator of Arg conversion towards neurotoxic vs. neuroprotective metabolites, placing Arg metabolism at the crossroads of neuronal health and injury. This review highlights how disruption of Arg homeostasis and downstream metabolic pathways may be linked to disease-specific alterations in arginase, becoming a feature of major neurodegenerative diseases. A central notion is that balanced Arg utilization is essential for brain cells: excessive arginase activity diverts Arg away from NO production and drives excessive generation of polyamines and downstream metabolites (GABA, acrolein), while insufficient arginase exposes cells to uncontrolled inflammation and excitotoxic damage. Arginase isoenzymes, through their specific cellular and subcellular localization, have specific capacities to link metabolic pathways with mechanisms of cellular death, dysfunction or survival, making them key mediators of how chronic metabolic dysregulation can drive neurodegeneration.

Therapeutically, the arginase/Arg pathway offers novel opportunities. Preclinical studies already show that modulating arginase activity and related metabolic pathways, whether by inhibitors like norvaline/DFMO or by supplementation strategies, can mitigate neurodegenerative pathology. A key challenge is to translate these findings into effective treatments, recognizing that a uniform therapeutic strategies are unlikely to be effective, given the diverse, cell- and disease-specific roles of arginase. Differential interventions will likely be required: arginase inhibition in AD and PD, versus arginase support in HD and ALS, ideally in cell/isoenzyme-specific manner. Importantly, arginase and its metabolites could also serve as diagnostic biomarkers of disease progression and treatment efficiency, aiding in disease monitoring and patient stratification for treatment and trials.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Martyna Nalepa: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization;
Aleksandra Skweres: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization;
Michał Węgrzynowicz: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

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Declaration of competing interest

None

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used OpenAI ChatGPT 5.2 in order to improve the language and readability. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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